

SMS Classifier and Extractor for Financial Tracking using NLP

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Abstract— This research proves the multimodal approach for filtering and extracting financial data from multilingual SMS messages is superior to traditional parsing methods like regex. It found Naive Bayes model outperformed other models in spam classification and the spaCy's custom-trained Named Entity Recognition (NER) model was able to extract financial data with a precision of nearly 93% on new forms of data.

Keywords— Spam detection, Natural Language Processing (NLP), Financial Data Extraction, Personal Finance Management, Named Entity Recognition (NER)

I. INTRODUCTION

The exponential surge in online financial transactions in India [1], exemplified by the staggering 113.95 billion digital transactions recorded in the financial year 2023 [2], signifies a profound shift towards digital banking convenience [3][4]. However, amidst the ease of conducting transactions through various platforms such as Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS), National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT), Unified Payments Interface (UPI), debit/credit cards and more [5], users encounter mounting challenges in effectively managing their financial data. The proliferation of Payment Service Providers (PSPs) adds another layer of complexity to personal finance management. Despite the digital trails left behind in the form of SMS messages, the lack of standardized formats, multilingual content, and diverse financial instruments hinder efficient data extraction and analysis.

Many users already use some form of tools for transaction logging. It may be a physical record on paper or a digital record in the form of emails, spreadsheets or apps [6]. Traditionally, both these methods rely on manual entry of data. Previous research at automation using SMS data paired with Regular Expression [7][8] lacked the accuracy and reliability. For a digital financial tracking application to be effective, it relies heavily on accurate transaction data to empower users in managing multiple financial instruments. By providing a consolidated perspective, such applications enable users to discern spending patterns [9], recognize trends [6], generate comprehensive reports, and facilitate savings [10] through informed decision-making [11]. Additionally, they aid users in setting financial objectives, such as saving for a down payment on a house or planning for retirement [12]. Consequently, ensuring the accuracy of underlying data is paramount for the efficacy of these applications, a requirement that current tools often fail to meet.

The use of machine learning in SMS has largely been limited to classification. Thus, a noticeable gap exists in research concerning data extraction from SMS using ML. With the increase in digital transactions and the growing need to manage them, our research aims to address these challenges by developing an intelligent system capable of discerning relevant SMS messages (filtering spam) and comprehending their contents to extract key data for automated transaction logging in a format which is ingestible by existing systems.

II. METHODOLOGY

To accurately extract information from the SMS, two models are required. The first model is used to classify SMS as spam or ham (i.e. not spam) and the other model is used to extract relevant information. The computational model for the pipeline consists of several main modules that perform their operations sequentially. These modules include language detection, pre-processing, spam detection, and extraction of transaction information. The following sections discuss each of these modules in detail.

Fig. 1 Proposed System

In this study, a dataset was sourced from Kaggle, a prominent online platform for hosting datasets and data science competitions. This dataset, titled “SMS Spam Collection Dataset,” comprises 5574 rows and 2 columns and was obtained from <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/uciml/sms-spam-collection-dataset>. The dataset was extended with additional real-world data consisting of 100 messages, 10 of which were spam, labeled manually. This data was only used in the final testing of the model.

For the text extraction model, due to the unavailability of a suitable dataset meeting our requirements for training a model, a new dataset was constructed by extracting SMS data from our phones and acquiring additional data from our peers. The resulting dataset consists of 500 rows with 2 columns: Raw and Annotated. The Raw column consists of SMS as it is, and the Annotated column consists of hand-annotated entities (in SpaCy format). The datasets cover various types of transactions, including UPI, Credit Card, Debit Card, Wallets, and Net Banking, from the following banks: AU Small Finance Bank, Canara Bank, Federal Bank (Fi), HDFC Bank, IDFC First Bank, India Post Payments Bank, Paytm Payments Bank (PBBL), State Bank of India (SBI), Union Bank of India (UBI). The dataset included 20 SMS in Marathi and 30 SMS in Hindi, while the rest were

in English. Subsequently, the dataset was then divided into training and testing with a ratio of 80:20, and texts from SBI were kept exclusively in the test dataset for verification of the model.

A. Pre-processing Text

The Pre-processing steps consist of SMS Filtering, Tokenization, Stemming, Deleting stopwords, and Vector representation of text.

Fig. 2 Text Pre-processing Flowchart

1) *Language detection*: Due to the multilingual nature of Transaction SMS to better serve customers, it is important to identify the language of the text and convert it to usable form. For our pipeline, we have used the googletrans module in Python, which provides a simple interface to Google Translate's API. The module is only applied if the text is not in English. For privacy, numerical values within the text are replaced with placeholder values before translation and subsequently restored post-translation.

2) *SMS Filtering*: This phase aims to separate transactional messages from other types of messages. We built a small set of rules containing a set of words that can be used to identify transactional messages. This helps to filter potential useful SMS messages.

3) *Tokenization*: Tokenization is the process of breaking down a text or a corpus into smaller units called tokens. These tokens can be words, phrases, symbols, or other meaningful elements. We used the NLTK library for this.

4) *Stemming and Stopwords Removal*: Stemming is a technique used to reduce words to their root or base form, called the stem. It involves removing suffixes or prefixes from words to obtain the core meaning. Stopwords are common words that frequently occur in a language but typically do not carry significant meaning. We utilized the NLTK library for the stemming and stopwords removal. We added words like "Dear", "Call", and "Report" to the stopwords list.

5) *Vector representation*: Text data is inherently symbolic, but machines need numerical representations for processing. Vector representations convert textual information into numerical vectors. It helps the data suitable for analysis [13]. The TfidfVectorizer function from the sklearn library was used to transform the corpus into a vector in our program.

B. Spam Detection

It refers to the process of identifying and filtering unwanted, unsolicited, or malicious messages from legitimate communication. This phase aims to identify and halt further processing of spam text. Here, spam text refers to text that is not a transactional SMS but pretends to be one. Examples include Offers of credit card approvals, fake credit messages used by gambling apps, and more. Due to the simple nature of these SMS, we have evaluated several Machine Learning (ML) models including Logistic Regression, Naïve Bayes, and Support Vector Machines based on labeled data consisting of spam and non-spam examples [13][14]. While the popularity of these algorithms [13][15][16][17][18] certainly played a role in their initial consideration, our selection went beyond a simple "most used" approach. These models are known for their effectiveness in text classification tasks [13][19], particularly with sparse and high-dimensional data like textual features.

1) *Logistic Regression*: It is a process of modeling the probability of a discrete outcome given an input variable. The most common logistic regression model is a binary outcome, something that can take two values, such as true/false, yes/no, and so on.

2) *Naïve Bayes*: It is a probabilistic classification model based on Bayes' theorem with an assumption of independence between features. It calculates the probability of each class given the input features and selects the class with the highest probability as the predicted class. In previous text classification studies [15], it has shown remarkable performance in various metrics. MultinomialNB (part of Sklearn) was utilized.

3) *Support Vector Machines*: The main objective of the SVM algorithm is to find the optimal hyperplane in an N-dimensional space that can separate the data points in different classes in the feature space. The hyperplane aims to maximize the margin between the closest points of different classes.

C. NLP Extractor

The ham messages will be processed further for information extraction. In previous studies, Regular Expressions (regex) patterns have been used for information extraction [7][8]. However, with a variety of banks, languages, and types of transactions in digital payments, it requires constant updates to the regex templates, making it less desirable. Thus, we decided to fine tune the NER model [20] from the spaCy library due to their speed and robustness [20]. At its core, language is a structured system governed by rules and symbols for conveying information. NLP's primary goal is to bridge the communication gap between humans and computers, enabling machines to interpret and respond to natural language input [21]. The model was trained on the custom-built labeled dataset to recognize various entities in the SMS like TRANSACTION_TYPE, AMOUNT, DATE, AVAILABLE_BALANCE, BANK_NAME, and more.

Benchmarked results from the research [13] show the fastest execution time for the Naive Baye Model while having the highest accuracy. The accuracy of the Naive Bayes Model closely matches the results of research by [17][21]. This is possible due to similar approaches in data processing steps. While more advanced approaches like Neural networks [14], Random Forest [17] and Transformers + ensemble learning [23] have been researched, their tradeoff of slower execution time [13][23] can be significant when running on smartphones which have limited CPU resources.

TABLE IIIIV
EVALUATION OF THE PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT MODELS

Classification model	Accuracy	
	Training data	Testing data
Logistic Regression	97.22%	65.1%
Support Vector Machine	98.11%	62.5%
Naive Bayes	98.45%	82.5%

The Naive Bayes model also performs better with fewer features (one feature in our case) due to its independence assumption and it tends to be less prone to overfitting compared to logistic regression and SVM. This is shown in the results when the models were evaluated on real-world data as shown in Table 2. All models dropped in accuracy while Naive Bayes still performed better. This highlights the need to train the model on more recent data.

B. Information Extraction

Previous studies for information extraction suggested using regular expressions [13]. For example, the research suggested regex to detect the amount in an SMS using “(\d+(\,|\.)+)+\d+”. The following matches the amount of “8000.00” but also matches any other sequence of numbers like a Reference Number “666777888999”. This shows the pitfall of using regex and highlights the need to understand the context for generalization of the model. This research, thus, proposes a NER model, which was fine tuned on our dataset to extract data from the SMS. The result is then converted into JSON format, making it easily consumable by other applications.

TABLE VVIVII
EVALUATION METRICS OF SPACY’S CUSTOM-TRAINED NER MODEL FOR INFORMATION EXTRACTION

Entity	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
CARD_NUMBER	0.958	0.958	0.958	25
TRANSACTION_TYPE	0.960	0.990	0.974	100
AMOUNT	0.919	0.989	0.953	100
DATE	0.980	1.000	0.990	100
AVAILABLE_BALANCE	0.818	0.857	0.837	25
BANK_NAME	0.979	0.939	0.958	100
TRANSACTION_ID	0.833	0.915	0.872	84
ACC_NUMBER	0.957	0.927	0.942	100

SENDER_NAME	0.786	0.846	0.815	16
RECEIVER_NAME	0.857	0.818	0.837	50
Micro Avg	0.929	0.946	0.938	700
Macro Avg	0.905	0.924	0.914	700
Weighted Avg	0.928	0.945	0.935	700

From the results in Table 3, we can observe the model was able to extract relevant entities like ACC_NUMBER, DATE, AMOUNT, etc. The support column signifies the number of rows in which that entity existed. When tested with data, including samples from SBI, which was excluded from the training set, the model achieved an overall precision of 92.8% and recall of 94.5%, indicating its effectiveness. We didn't observe any regression when using translated text for extraction. However, we observed a notable challenge arises from distinguishing between ACC_NUMBER and TRANSACTION_ID. Bank account numbers typically range from 11 to 16 digits, while transaction ids are commonly 12 digits long. This leads to misclassifications, particularly when encountering 12-digit account numbers used by certain banks like Paytm Payments Bank, which may erroneously be labeled as TRANSACTION_ID or vice versa.

An example text from the dataset- *"Rs. 8000.00 debited from your A/c XXXXXXXXXXXX9295 using UPI on 06-02-2024 21:20:55 to someone@upi. UPI Ref No 666777888999 - Federal Bank."*. The system was able to extract the following entities : *"{'receiver_name': 'someone@upi', 'amount': '8000.00', 'acc_number': 'XXXXXXXXXXXX9295', 'transaction_id': '666777888999', 'date': '06-02-2024', 'transaction_type': 'credit'}"*.

When compared with previous research [11], which utilized regular expression, the results had an accuracy of 83% while extracting fewer features and requiring an additional model to check the type of transaction (debit/credit). In contrast, the NER model shows an impressive 92.8% weighted average precision while managing to extract a richer set of features from the SMS. This model is a major improvement and will significantly help to automate text extraction for transaction logging, helping to save significant time for users. Banks and other institutions can also integrate this system to create user profiles and better match them with loans, insurance, ratings and other services with more confidence.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study focused on developing two models for SMS message processing tasks, focusing on classification and data extraction. The models evaluated for classification consisted of Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes and SVM. The models performed similarly in the range of 97-99% accuracy on the test data. However, the Naive Bayes model performed better when exposed to real-world data, scoring an accuracy of 82.52%. This gap is due to the outdated nature of the dataset, which needs to account for the evolution of spam messages over time. The extraction model based on NER offered a 92.8% precision and 94.5% recall on test data, showcasing the overall generalization capabilities of the model, as the test data featured data from banks that were excluded in training data.

In both models, we have identified a lack of new datasets to be a significant challenge for real-world usage. As spam messages continually evolve in content and structure, relying on an old dataset limits the model's effectiveness in accurately classifying new and emerging spam patterns, rendering it less useful in real-world usage. The dataset of only 500 rows limited the extraction mode. As a result, there is potential for future work to expand the training data, enabling further refinement and enhancement of the model's capabilities in generalization.

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